

Breaking out of the Gricean vicious cycle: Let's divorce semantics and just agree that there is no meaning in language

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The existing theories of meaning are classifiable into semantic and foundational categories. After a brief overview of these categories, the current paper will dwell on a discussion of what has urged pragmaticists to endorse a dovetailing of semantics and pragmatics in their attempts at presenting a comprehensive and exhaustive account of meaning. The paper then uses Balkhi's analogy of 'the elephant in the dark room' to argue that (a) all of the existing theories of meaning are inadequate, and that (b) the Gricean vicious cycle is also the product of pragmaticists' mistaking complimentary distribution for inclusional distribution. Arguing in favor of a physiological theory of meaning, the paper concludes that a comprehensive theory of meaning has to be a theory of human brain and/or mind and should be foundational.

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1. Introduction

Working in the tradition of applied linguistics for over three decades now, I would normally be expected to bring a (pre-)structured genre to bear on the 'structuration' of any journal article I seek to write up, but this is not one of those times; this time I am breaking out of the imposed pre-planned generic structure of journal articles and would rather follow a path that is not clear to myself yet but will unfold in front of me with every step I take. I deem this approach necessary since the content that I have sought to discuss in this article has left me with no conventional, nor any conventionalized, option. In fact, I am like the little boy who entered a jungle on the back of his horse late at night, couldn't see a step, and told his horse that he couldn't see, then the horse asked, "can you see your next step?" only to receive a 'yes' upon hearing of which he told the boy, "then, just take that." So let's stop beating about the bush and start cutting to the chase.

The notion of 'meaning' has haunted philosophers, logicians, and—more

recently—linguists for perhaps the whole history of mankind, but no one is still sure what meaning really and sincerely is. Does meaning exist at all? If yes, is it static or dynamic? Is it *a priori* or *a posteriori*? Is meaning a process or a product? Is it existent or emergent? Is it ‘deontological’ or ‘teleological’—to borrow terms from Kamm (2007) on ethics? Can we have an adequate theory of meaning? Should such a theory be ‘semantic’, ‘pragmatic’, ‘foundational’, or otherwise? Can ‘symbolic logic’ account for meaning adequately? These and a plethora of other similar questions are ‘fundamental’ questions that have not received precise and adequate answers yet.

The first people to break the ice were perhaps ancient Greek philosophers (e.g., Aristotle, Zeno, and Pythagoras, inter alia), but their works have been taken up by scholars ever since the age of enlightenment, developed into what has come to be known as symbolic logic, and later claimed by Chomsky (1969) who suggested his notorious and ‘formal’ concept of ‘interpretive’ semantics, which was, of course, ruled out by the pragmatic camp—i.e., people like Mey (2001), Rumfitt (1993), Segal (1989), Weizman and Dascal (1991), Wolfson (1989), and myself, whom Chomsky has tacitly and politely called ‘informal’ linguists. Nevertheless, we ardently believe that we are right and tell the truth, nothing but truth, and the whole of it no matter whether we are branded as ‘informal’ linguists or hailed and praised as proponents of true scholarship.

With that out of the way, I shall focus on my own perspective on the question of meaning in this paper. I will first review, albeit briefly, what has already been claimed about/on meaning by people on many different ‘puny’ podiums (all collectively belonging into either of the three mega-camps of semantics, philosophy, or pragmatics); then, I will use the methodology proposed by Francois Bacon (1620)—i.e., his *pars destruens* and *pars construens* dichotomy—to rule out other theories of meaning and propose my own outlook and perspective which I feel is much more adequate in explaining what meaning sincerely is.

2. Background

In this section, I shall present a brief review of the existing literature on ‘theories of meaning’. This may make the section monotonous and redundant for the reader who is versed in the field, but I shall also intersperse the review with my own critical thought and stance so that the versed reader will find it tolerable.

Looking at the existing scholarly thought on them from an Archimedean standpoint, one can easily classify ‘theories of meaning’ into two major categories: (1) semantic, or (2) foundational. The former set has mainly been proposed by logicians as well as linguists, but the latter has come mainly from

philosophers. More recently, though, a third camp—i.e., the pragmatic camp—has sought to present its own pragmatic perspective on meaning; note that here the term ‘pragmatic’ is used in both its linguistic and its philosophical senses. Semantic theories have just one job to do: to assign some kind of semantic ‘content’ to forms of language such that a meaning-form association is built; foundational theories, on the other hand, are mainly philosophical in the sense that they assume that there are ‘facts’ (e.g., distributions—i.e., inclusional, overlapping, complimentary, or equivalent—abstractions, generalizations, psychological facts, sociological facts, contexts, etc.) which make it possible for language forms to have any semantic content. In other words, such theories are not concerned about/with the association between form and meaning, but about/with the ‘facts’ that give room to such association to happen. In this connection, Lewis (1970, p. 9) said:

I distinguish two topics: first, the description of possible languages or grammars as abstract semantic systems whereby symbols are associated with aspects of the world; and, second, the description of the psychological and sociological facts whereby a particular one of these abstract semantic systems is the one used by a person or population. Only confusion comes of mixing these two topics.

In fact, confusion has indeed come of mixing the two. The first was supposed to answer a very simple question:

- What is the meaning of a given symbol (e.g., a word, a sign, etc.) for a given person/group/nation?

The second, on the other hand, was supposed to answer a somewhat complicated and more fundamental question:

- What/Which facts about that person/group/nation make that symbol mean what it means?

The theories that answer the former question are semantic in nature, but those that answer the latter are foundational or fundamental; nevertheless, I do not see why the proponents of each mega-camp should ever want to de-rail the other. Is it not possible to talk about the existence of an ‘inclusional distribution’ here, one that assumes semantic theories are included inside foundational theories—i.e., are part and parcel of them? Would it not be possible to reconcile the two mega-camps by telling them that your theories are in reality two different sorts/arrays of theories each designed to answer a different question. Nevertheless, semantic and foundational theories of meaning possess different levels of observational/descriptive/explanatory adequacy (cf. Green, 2006), but again this is a ‘relative’ issue in the sense that

the adequacy of a theory should be judged on the basis of what it claims to account for—i.e., its validity.

Nevertheless, there is a third mega-camp that (1) does not associate itself with either the ‘semantic’ or the ‘foundational’ camp, (2) nor does it accept the existence of any facts about the meanings of language forms (e.g., Kripke 1982; Quine 1960; Soames 1997); I would, however, argue that this mega-camp belongs in the foundational mega-camp since their skepticism is essentially a philosophical perspective on meaning. I myself do agree with the people in this third mega-camp, but I feel there are neuro-socio-psychological explanations that can adequately account for ‘why’ linguistic forms mean ‘what’ they mean to people who acquire and use them; note that this encompasses both of the questions that I ‘bulleted’ above, so I can argue that the theory I will broach in the following sections may be a more adequate theory than the existing ones.

It should also be noted that each natural language (e.g., English, Persian, etc.) has its own semantics, and this creates an in-principle issue for semantic theories: how is it ever possible to propose an all-encompassing semantic theory that adequately accounts for meaning in all languages of the world in view of the fact that we know each language has its own specific semantics? Well, semantic theories have sought to explain what the correct form for a ‘semantics’ for any given natural language is (e.g., Heim & Kratzer, 1998; Montague, 1974; Moss, 2012).

Semantic theories of meaning stand on two basic tenets: (1) any sentence in any language is either true or false (i.e., has a truth condition), and (2) its truth condition is a function of what it expresses (i.e., the information it encodes or its ‘proposition’/‘explicature’). Semantic theories of meaning bring these two tenets to bear on their explanation of how parts of a sentence and the context in which the sentence has been used work in tandem to give its ‘proposition’ the ‘truth condition’ it has. In general, semantic theories of meaning can roughly be categorized into two classes: (1) classical semantic theories, and (2) alternative semantic theories. The former includes (a) the theory of reference, (b) possible worlds semantics, (c) Russellian semantics, and (d) Fregean semantics—to name only a few. The latter, however, includes Davidsonian semantics, (b) internalist semantics, (c) inferentialist semantics, (d) dynamic semantics, and (e) expressivist semantics—again, to name only a few (Heim and Kratzer, 1998). Note that ‘classical’ and ‘alternative’ are arbitrary—i.e., only appellations used for ease of classification—but they are not ‘essential’ in any philosophical sense.

The ‘theory of reference’, which can be traced back to Frege’s (1879; 1892) attempts at formalizing mathematical inferences in arithmetic and algebra (cf. Graff Fara, 2015; Jeshion, 2015), assumes that any ‘monadic’ (in the

Pythagorean sense of the word) or ‘kernel’ sentence¹ comprises a linear set of ‘syntagmatic’ slots/pigeon holes (i.e., one function, operation or relation called a ‘predicator’ along with its arity, adicity, rank, valency or degree called ‘argument’) that can be filled with lexical ‘paradigmatic’ fillers (i.e., lexemes from the speaker’s ‘mental lexicon’); note that this is exactly what Chomsky has skillfully ‘owned’, so to speak, in his discussions of deep structure (cf. Chomsky, 1969, 1975) and x-bar theory (Chomsky, 1981). Seen in this light, a kernel sentence expressing a proposition, can either be true or false, but its truth condition depends on the sense-reference connection between its component parts—i.e., its external argument, predicator, and internal argument(s)—and their corresponding real-world ‘referents’—be they ‘objects’ or ‘relations’. Thus, “Macron is a liberal” is only true when the referent of ‘Macron’ (i.e., the man in the real world who is referred to as Macron) honestly and sincerely belongs in the liberal party (cf. Heim & Kratzer, 1998). When it comes to compound and complex sentences (and also simple sentences that are not ‘kernel’), establishing truth conditions is not that simple; first, they have to be broken down into their kernels, then the truth condition of each kernel sentence should be identified, and then all of the values should be charted in a ‘truth table’ before one can decide whether the compound or complex sentence is true or false.

The question that remains is whether a ‘reference theory’ of meaning is adequate? Frege himself got puzzled when he decided to establish the true conditions of his famous examples “Hesperus is Hesperus” and “Hesperus is Phosphorus” (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2015). Likewise, Quine’s (1970 [1986], pp. 8-9) examples, “All cordates are cordates” and “All cordates are renates,” recount the same story. Computing truth conditions gets even more complicated when one considers more complex language forms such as ‘implicatures’, ‘presuppositions’, ‘reported speech’, ‘belief reports’, ‘deixis’, ‘modals’, ‘temporal modifiers’, ‘existential quantifiers’, ‘non-extensional contexts’, and ‘*de se*, *de dicto*, and *de re* meanings’—to name only a few—where truth-condition values go beyond reference. These constructions have persuaded linguists to give preference to semantic theories over reference theories since (a) mental states such as beliefs, (b) modal properties such as possibility or necessity, and (c) epistemic properties such as ‘*a posterioricity*’ versus ‘*a prioricity*’ add new content to explicatures or, literally speaking, things that are expressed by sentences. A reference theory of meaning lacks adequacy in that it is not able to account for such qualities. Take this example where ‘cohesion’ creates an issue:

- (1) a. John is from Glasgow.
- b. He is not stingy.
- c. John is from Glasgow, but he is not stingy.

Like ‘reference theories’ of meaning, ‘proposition theories’ (i.e., those that claim that subsentential linguistic expressions also comprise some sort of ‘proposition’ or ‘content’ in addition to reference) are inadequate in that they (a) fail to explain why Frege’s “Hesperus is Hesperus” is tautological and trivial whereas his “Hesperus is Phosphorus” is not, and (b) cannot account for changes in truth values when parts of a sentence are ‘substituted’ with similar elements:

- (2) a. John believes that *Macron is the president of France*.
 b. John believes that *Modi is the prime minister of India*.

While (2)a and (2)b express different propositions, they have the same truth value—albeit if we sincerely know that John ‘believes’ both propositions are ‘true’; hence, Frege’s (1879; 1892) famous aphorism, ‘content determines reference’. By this token, a semantic theory of meaning assigns some sort of ‘content’ to any given ‘expression’—or is at least expected to do so. However, this is not the case when it comes to ‘deixis’, ‘personal pronouns’, and other indexicals—or situation-bound utterances (SBUs) or context-dependent expressions. ‘I’, when uttered by me, has one reference, but a totally different reference when uttered by someone else in a different ‘context’ or ‘situation’.

As such, an adequate theory of meaning needs rules that (a) have been called ‘character’, and (b) are/determine functions from contexts to contents (Kaplan, 1989)—i.e., character + context → content → reference. The question that remains unanswered is, “Is it ever possible to find any expression in any language that is not context-sensitive?” Take this example:

- (3) a. Ten years ago, ‘NASA landing Mars rover on Mars’ was a headline.
 b. In ten years, my math teacher will be dead.

(3)a and (3)b show that, besides context and content, ‘circumstance of evaluation’ (i.e., the possible state of the actual world at the time of any given utterance) also plays a part in assigning truth values to propositions; hence, ‘double-indexing semantics’, à la Kaplan (1989), Kamp (1971), Lewis (1980), and Perry (1979) (i.e., character + context → content + circumstance of evaluation → reference), which gives prominence to both (a) contexts of utterance and (b) circumstances of evaluation as determiners of meaning—See also Kripke (1972) on ‘rigid designators’. Hence, possible worlds semantics, which assumes that the meaning of an expression is what it would stand for if the world were a certain way (cf. Carnap, 1947). Possible worlds semantics argues that (1) contents are nothing other than ‘intensions’ (i.e., functions from circumstances of evaluation to a reference), and (2) characters are functions from contexts to intensions (see also Lewis, 1970)—i.e., character + context → intension + circumstance of evaluation → reference. As

such, a proposition (or the intension of a sentence) is a function from possible worlds to truth-values.

By this token, possible worlds semantics augments the theory of reference by adding an extra layer (i.e., intensions) on top of it. Nevertheless, possible worlds semantics is inadequate in that it cannot precisely account for sentence pairs such as:

- (4) a. Jack believes that Hesperus is Hesperus.
- b. Jack believes that Hesperus is Phosphorus.

(4)a and 4(b) are propositional attitude ascriptions (i.e., sentences that take the form “Subject believes/asserts that *S*.”). PAs can express the same proposition ‘if and only if’ it is by no means possible for them to differ in terms of their truth-values (cf. Soames, 1988; Stalnaker, 1984; Yalcin, 2018). Nevertheless, PAs oftentimes, if not always, glower at this expectation and defy it (Nolan, 2013). This is exactly where Russellian semantics enters the scene: a proposition is structured in the sense that it has constituents each of which bears some part of the meaning of the whole sentence that expresses the proposition. Nevertheless, no one knows precisely what sort of things comprises the constituents of propositions. Russellianism would argue that such constituents include (a) relations, (b) properties, (c) objects, and (d) functions.² Nevertheless, the so-called Millian-Russellian semantics is not without its critics; if the referent of a proper name is the object for which it stands, then what about fancy names (i.e., empty names) such as Mordor?—See also Braun (1993). The Millian-Russellian semantics also fails to account for Frege’s puzzle in which ‘Hesperus is Hesperus’ is obviously a trivial tautology, but ‘Hesperus is Phosphorus’ is an informative sentence that needs more attention when it comes to the computation of its truth condition. The problem gets worse when Frege’s pair of sentences is embedded in PAs (See example 4 above).

To account for the inadequacy of Russellian semantics in explaining Frege’s puzzle, some scholars (e.g., Salmon, 1986; Soames, 2002) have argued that our assumptions are misguided in that we happen to confuse the propositions encapsulated within the pragmatic intensions of speakers’ language use with the propositions that are semantically expressed by the same language forms in a given context. This is exactly where the semantics-pragmatics debate enters the scene—as we will see below. Salmon (1986), in specific, used the term ‘propositional guises’ (or PGs) to argue that the same proposition might be interpreted or even believed under different ‘guises’ most probably because hearers or readers bring distinct mental representations to bear on their interpretations of propositions and in the mean time they fail to integrate pieces of stored information (Braun & Saul, 2002); this claim maybe

considered as a precursor to the famous Relevance Theory (RT). Nevertheless, there are other people in the Russellian camp (e.g., Fine, 2007; Taschek, 1995) who have given up on the idea that sentence pairs that differ only in terms of the substitution of a proper name with the same content—example (4) above—will have to afford the same proposition, whereby allowing such sentence pairs to genuinely differ in terms of their truth conditions. That is, a pair of sentences can indeed differ in meaning even though they have the same intensions.

Granting the last position paves the way for putting an end to Millian-Russellian semantics and endorsing Fregean semantics since Frege himself responded to his own puzzle by arguing that two names (e.g., Hesperus and Phosphorus) can refer to the same object and at the same time express different meanings—i.e., they differ in truth value (Frege 1892 [1960]). Unlike the proponents of the Russellian camp who saw the constituents of a sentence in terms of objects, properties, and relations, Fregean semantics sees them as ‘senses’—i.e., ‘ways of thinking’ about, objects, properties, and relations (or ‘modes of presentation’). As such, an objective ‘proper name’ in language has an objective ‘reference’ in the real world (i.e., the object it refers to, called ‘referent’ by some), but the way each person understands the connection between the ‘proper name’ and its ‘reference/referent’ is quite subjective and person-specific. Frege (1892 [1960]) uses the ‘Moon, its telescope image, and individuals’ retinal images from their standpoints of observation’ as an analogy to explain his sense-reference conception. By the same token, a ‘dictionary’ is differentiated from a ‘lexicon’ in the sense that the former is like the telescope in Frege’s analogy, but the latter refers to each individual’s mental representation of that ‘realia’ (i.e., physical dictionary). In other words, one physical dictionary—such as *Oxford English Dictionary*—can change into as many mental lexicons as there are English speakers, learners, users, etc.

Nevertheless, Fregean semantics has been called into question on the ground that, instead of using already existing entities (i.e., objects, properties, or relations), it has introduced a new entity (i.e., senses) to account for Frege’s puzzle. Although I understand the concerns of the critics of Frege about Occam’s razor, I don’t see why this should be a problem if neurological research can show that senses have psychological reality. My assumption is that Frege’s critics have totally misunderstood Occam’s razor: if two theories have exactly the ‘same’ degree of explanatory adequacy, the minimal one is to be preferred, added that ‘minimalizing’ theories is always possible if only we use symbols (such as arithmetic symbols and notations) instead of long descriptive texts. For instance, if $E = MC^2$ were written in text format, it would perhaps be ‘un-minimal’, so to speak, and much longer than a thick book. Are Millian-Russellian semantics and Fregean semantics of the same degree of explanatory adequacy? I doubt it. Frege himself was cognizant enough to

introduce his own ‘criterion of difference for senses’, a weapon loaded and used for scowling defiantly at the attacks leveled against his semantics on the part of the proponents of the Millian-Russellian camp: *S* and *S** have different senses ‘if and only if’ a given rational logical agent who understood *S* and *S** could, on reflection, argue that *S* is true/false without accepting that *S** is true/false (Frege, 1906). This criterion can, nevertheless, be rephrased to encompass sentence pairs in which one ‘content’ is substituted by another—i.e., differ only in ‘coreferentiality’ or the substitution of *e* for *e**. Seen from the lens of Fregeanism, the ‘content/sense’ of a ‘name’ is more than its ‘reference’; rather, it is the condition that the reference satisfies; hence, Fregean descriptivism.

Fregean descriptivism assumed that senses are essentially condition-bound definite descriptions, but I would refer to each description as an arbitrary ‘tag’ or a ‘temporary identity’ such that Hesperus is one tag and Phosphorus another. The serious attack leveled against Fregean descriptivism has come to be known as the ‘modal argument’ (e.g., Kripke, 1972, and Marcus, 1961). To defy this attack, the Fregean camp has opted for ‘non-descriptive’ Fregeanism (e.g., Caplan, 2005; Dummett, 1981; Evans, 1981; McDowell, 1977; Plantinga, 1978; Soames, 1998, 2002; Sosa, 2001) which dovetails ‘Fregean’ and ‘possible worlds’ semantics—an epistemic two-dimensionalist perspective ardently promulgated by Chalmers (2004, 2006). Nevertheless, Fregeanism still fails to adequately account for ‘indexicality’ (Perry, 1977) and PAs.

To prove that Russell and Frege were not the only gamers in town, (1) Davidsonian semantics, (2) internalist semantics, (3) inferentialist semantics, (4) dynamic semantics, and (5) expressivist semantics were introduced and promulgated as alternatives to classical semantic theories.

Attacking classical semantics on the assumption that they trivialize the job of a semantic theory by reducing it to a pairing of expressions with entities, Wittgenstein (1953, §120) argued:

You say: the point isn’t the word, but its meaning, and you think of the meaning as a thing of the same kind as the word, though also different from the word. Here the word, there the meaning. The money, and the cow that you can buy with it.

Wittgenstein’s anti-theoretical stance and his aversion to “meanings as entities” were taken up by subsequent scholars (e.g., Davidson, 1967) who argued that a semantic theory should be a theory of truth (cf. Tarski, 1944) which encompasses (a) the references/objects to which proper nouns refer, and (b) the set of things that satisfy any given predicate in language. As such, Davidsonian semantics—i.e., his competent theory of meaning—is essentially

an upcycled version of the reference theory of meaning (see note #1 below on kernel/monadic sentences). For any given sentence in a language, Davidsonian semantics assumes a *T-sentence* that delineates the set of conditions that have to be met for that sentence to be true (i.e., *S* is *T* in *L* iff *p*). For instance, the sentence 'John shouts' is *T* (in the given language) if and only if John shouts. Davidsonian semantics should be hailed for its 'parsimony' as it has divorced Russellian propositions and Fregean senses (cf. Burge, 1986; Larson & Ludlow, 1993; Lepore & Loewer, 1989; Schiffer, 1987; Soames, 2002). It has its own shortcomings, though.

Nevertheless, Foster (1976) and Larson and Segal (1995) have found two problems in Davidsonian semantics: (1) the *extension* problem, and (2) the *information* problem. It has been argued that '*T* in *L* iff *p*' does not give the meaning of *S* whereas a theory of meaning should do so. Since the theory assumes 'at least' one *T* sentence for any *S*, this means that there may be more than one *T* sentences for that *S*, one of which is interpretive and the other(s) non-interpretive; hence, the extension problem. Moreover, the truth of what is expressed by *S* is supposed to be judged on the basis of the *T* sentence, but English speakers who do not know Persian, for instance, would not be able to understand the *S* in the sentence: "Tehran paay-e takht-e ?Iran ?ast" is *T* in Persian iff Tehran is the capital of Iran. Hence, the information problem (cf. Ray, 2014; Soames, 1992).

Along the same lines, internalist semantics argues that mind-world reference relations do not have to play any part in semantic theorizing (Chomsky, 2000). The idea is that the workings of human mind do not need to be explained by connecting it to the external physical world; hence, the nomenclature 'internalist'. This perspective denies reference, truth conditions, extensions, etc., and argues, instead, that if names are used to refer to things in an arbitrary way, or sentences are used to say true or false things about the external world, this does not mean that what we refer to or claim to be true comprises the meaning of what we express; rather, we are only using one of the potentials of names or sentences. Pietroski (2018) argues that (a) meaning, seen from the internalist perspective, is an instruction "for how to build concepts of a special sort" (p. 36), and that (b) concepts are mental representations of a certain kind—a view that I clearly associate with because I do believe that we (1) use our five senses to explore the world, (2) form perceptions based on our sensory input, then (3) find regularities in our perceptions through induction to make generalizations or form concept(ion)s, which may finally (4) turn up into theories or laws of nature through deduction and abstraction. This is basically an argument that (a) allows concepts to have extensions but (b) denies the same right for expressions of natural languages and (c) accounts for polysemy—e.g., 'line' in fishing lines, Euclidean lines, telephone lines, etc. (cf. McGilvray, 1998).

A third gamer in town is ‘inferentialist semantics’. While internalist semantics rejected truth conditions altogether, inferentialist semantics accepts them but argues that they do not play a fundamental role in a semantic theory (cf. Brandom, 2000). The *a priori* grip of classical semantics on the notion of truth is essentially reversed in inferentialist semantics. Likewise, dynamic semantics—the fourth gamer in town—holds that the primary job of a theory of meaning is not to pair sentences and evaluate their truth conditions in light of the propositions they express but to account for how context affects language use—i.e., context change potentials (cf. Rothschild & Yalcin, 2016). Unlike other alternatives to classical semantics, dynamic semantics does not do away with ‘content’, ‘word-world relations’, and other claims of classical semantics but complements them. Examples of this approach to semantics include Kamp’s (1981) discourse representation theory and Heim’s (1982) file change semantics, but I would also admit that the majority of ‘pragmatic’ accounts of meaning (e.g., Relevance Theory, the Wittgensteinian theory of language games, etc.) fall in this category (cf. Lewis, 2014; Stojnić, 2019).

Unlike the other four gamers in town, expressivist semantics is essentially a philosophical metaethical perspective on meaning that has sought to understand the epistemological, metaphysical, psychological, and semantic foundations of thought, ethics, talk, and practice. Expressivist semantics works with mental states and argues that mental states expressed in sentences concerning ethics are different from those expressed in ‘factual’ sentences. The mental states expressed in non-ethical sentences are, à la expressivist semanticists, beliefs whereas those expressed in ethical sentences (e.g., commands, exclamations, plans, etc.) are not (cf. Ayer, 1936; Gibbard, 1990; Hare, 1952). For instance, ‘Sodomy is wrong’ is an ethical expression that represents the mental state of ‘planning’ not to commit sodomy. Expressivist semantics, as such, sees language as a machine that encompasses both ethical and non-ethical bits; nevertheless, it cannot adequately account for Frege-Geach problem—i.e., the interactions between the two types of language bits (cf. Geach, 1960, 1965; Searle, 1962; Schroeder, 2008). See also Yalcin (2007) on ‘epistemic modality’, Moss (2013) on ‘knowledge ascriptions’, and MacFarlane (2016) on ‘vagueness’.

All in all, the theories of meaning proposed by semantic and foundational camps have their pros and cons which were briefly reviewed above. In the next section, a brief *pars destruens*, à la Bacon (1620), is presented. It will then be followed by a *pars construens* and a discussion.

3. Pars destruens

It was noted above that all theories of meaning to-day lack complete adequacy and fail in some way or another. Part of this failure is probably due to their

approaches to theorizing. I would argue that semantic theories have failed because of their ardent adherence to ‘math’ and ‘arithmetic’, and foundational theories have failed because of their adherence to what can be called ‘paradigm’.

Semantic theories of meaning, especially ‘reference’ theories, have assumed that language is reducible to monadic sentences—that have functions, operations or relations called ‘predicators’ along with their arities, adicities, ranks, valencies or degrees called ‘arguments’—that can be either true or false. The aspiration for this way of looking at human language has most probably come from the paragon of pure sciences—i.e., mathematics. It seems as if all semantic theories of meaning have taken it for granted that human language comprises a set of *a priori* elements and constituents that might be tantamount to algebraic digits and operations. This Inside-the-box thinking has empowered such theories to also take fundamental concepts such as generalization, abstraction, relation, form, and system for granted. After all, it would be quite reasonable for people like Russell, Frege, and Chomsky—to name only a few—to endorse such an approach to meaning that assumes *a priori* that *a priori* theories of meaning are to be preferred since their entire trainings have been in (a) techniques and (b) the application of those techniques to problems. As such, the varied techniques of arithmetic, geometry, and algebra were brought to bear on emulating the ‘methods’ and ‘pedagogy’ of tackling issues of meaning in a natural language with the outcome that their theories of meaning have probably been practical but not that intellectual—due to the fact that they have all dwelled on rules of operation, and have done so almost exclusively. Their misconception has perhaps been such that students of semantics would and should learn to perform their proposed operations without knowing their conceptual pedestals or calling them into question. Needless to say, the proponents of the semantic camp have got so imbued with practical techniques and operations as well as methodology that they rarely doubt their conceptual foundations. Nevertheless, my criticism is by no means trying to deny or invalidate the potentials of semantic theories of meaning for (a) skillful handling, (b) responsible analysis, and (c) finding truth-values in language expressions, but my point is that we cannot and should not take such theories as comprehensive and exhaustive theories capable of answering epistemic questions about the nature of meaning.

Likewise, foundational theories of meaning, too, have failed to afford complete adequacy in that they have apparently tried to think out of the box—although I doubt it—at the cost of divorcing what is going on inside the box. While semantic theories of meaning have been informed by math and arithmetic (and to a lesser degree by symbolic logic), foundational theories have most probably been spurred by what has come to be known as ‘paradigm’. A

paradigm is originally an example or illustration meant to teach something indirectly, and there is some logic to it, but remains there through imitation even after the original logic is no longer at work. This has been demonstrated by the famous ‘five monkeys experiment’ in psychology (Maestriperieri, 2012).

In a nutshell, the experiment says if you put five monkeys in a cage where a bunch of bananas is hanging from the ceiling and there is a ladder leading to it, the monkeys will climb up to the bananas. Now, if you punish all monkeys by giving the whole cage an electric shock once a monkey climbs up the ladder, the other monkeys gradually learn to beat the climbing monkey to prevent it from climbing the ladder, a behavior that will stop the shock and group punishment. Now if you replace each of the five monkeys—one at a time—with a new monkey, the same behavior will keep repeating even in the absence of punishment. Gradually a time will come when all five monkeys have been replaced by new monkeys, there has been no punishment for them whatsoever, but the beating behavior keeps repeating any time any monkey climbs the ladder. A paradigm has formed. The original logic—i.e., electric shock—no longer exists, but new monkey groups keep beating the new climbing monkeys simply because they have seen other monkeys do the same.

This is probably what has happened in sciences; there has been a time when people talked about elite concepts such as ‘adequacy’, ‘parsimony’, ‘Occam’s razor’, and so on, and papers got rejected in peer-review process because they had not observed those probably logical principles, but this has changed into a paradigm—or a ‘gavel’ if you will (cf. Kaplan, 1964; Maslow, 1966)—with the outcome that new ‘monkeys’ take it for granted any time one daring monkey ventures to break out of the paradigm. By the same token, foundational theories of meaning have, metaphorically-speaking, found themselves confined within the confines of the walls of ‘explanatory adequacy’, ‘parsimony’, ‘Occam’s razor’, and so forth—taken-for-granted revelations that transpire whatever happens within the confines of the walls of sciences. Ironically, no one has dared to call these most-probably misguided ‘narratives’ into question: Why on earth should they ever be taken for granted as divine unexpendable revelations?

4. Pars construens

What went before has motivated people working in (linguistic) pragmatics to develop their own theories of thought, mind, and language. By pragmatics I mean the area of scientific inquiry that dwells on the interface between sociology, psychology, linguistics and philosophy and aims at accounting for language through a lens focused on the ‘knowledge of the world’ and of the ‘speakers’ (cf. Falk, 1978). When meaning is viewed from such a lens, the question that needs to be answered is: How many ‘thingamabobs’ contribute

to meaning? Well, the simple answer is ‘virtually everything’ including context, structure, lexis, the food you eat, whether you are on cocaine, air pressure, cohesion/coherence, speaker’s/listener’s silence, fluctuations in a speaker’s way of speaking, etc. I will expatiate on this below, but let’s now review the existing scholarly ‘pragmatic’ thought on meaning.

All in all, pragmatics does not see language in terms of meaning but in terms of intentions, games, acts, narratives, and the like. It not only looks for meaning inside sentence constituents, but also inside texture, cohesion and coherence, speakers, hearers, speech situations/events/acts, language games, power games, (con)text, and so forth. The major figures in pragmatics who talked about meaning and intention were philosophers (of language)—e.g., Austin (1962, 1963, 1975), Bakhtin (1986), Grice (1957, 1989), Jakobson (1960), Malinowski (1923), Searle (1969, 1975, 1979, 1981), Strawson (1964), Wittgenstein (1953). Nevertheless, the first scholar to notice a problem in pragmatic theories of meaning was Grice (1957), whose ‘chicken or egg’ perspective—i.e., the so-called semantics/pragmatics debate—fueled a chain of hot debates in subsequent decades. One extremely important case in point is the book *Pragmatics and Philosophy: Connections and Ramifications* by Capone (2019), which is a critical ‘anthology’, so to speak, of existing scholarly thought on the ‘semantics/pragmatics’ debate, albeit from a philosophical perspective.

The backbone of the so-called semantics/pragmatics debate is that meaning has two components: (1) a semantic component—pertaining to that portion of meaning residing inside ‘contentive’ sentence constituents—which is static, context-independent, *a priori*, stable and literal; and (2) a pragmatic component that is context-sensitive, dynamic, *a posteriori*, and most probably emergent. The 64-million-dollar chicken-or-egg question, then, is, “Which one takes its input from which?” This has come to be known as ‘Grice’s circle’ or ‘Gricean vicious cycle’ (Capone, 2019; Fiorin, 2022; Levinson, 2000). In this connection, the Gricean cannon has assumed that pragmatics takes its input from semantics, but subsequent researchers—specifically the relevance-theoretic camp and its major figures Sperber and Wilson (1986)—have assumed that semantics takes its input from pragmatics. Hence, concerns of circularity. As intriguing as it may seem, both camps seem to have taken it for granted that (a) semantics and pragmatics are modular, and that (b) they are in complimentary distribution. Seriously?

This kind of outlook on the issues of meaning by all of the scholars introduced hitherto reminds me of the famous ‘elephant in a dark room’ analogy proposed around 1000 years ago by Jalāl al-Dīn Muḥammad Balkhī (1258/2019)—the great Persian philosopher and poet ‘unlawfully’ owned by Turkey and well-known as Rūmī in the Anglo-American world—in his famous

book *Masnavi-ye-Ma'navi*. An elephant is in a dark room, people enter the room one at a time, touch some part of its body, and—because they cannot see the whole of the elephant—they give it different names based on their touch experiences. The one touching its back calls it a bed, the one touching its trunk calls it a chimney, the one touching its leg calls it a pillar, and so forth. If someone had turned on a lamp so that they could see the whole story from an Archimedean point, they all would have called it an elephant. By the same token, it seems as if we all have been fooled by our ‘cognitive tunnel visions’ (cf. Ausubel, 1963), and tend to endorse our ‘confirmation biases’ (Goldacre, 2008) since we are all ‘thinking inside the box’. Nevertheless, people concerned with the question of meaning have failed to get rid of their confirmation biases in the past few decades and have kept getting ever more entangled within the web they have been ignorantly weaving around themselves since the start of their scientific journey.

In an attempt to break out of this web, Capone (2019) has heavily expatiated upon the notion of the ‘cancellability/non-cancellability’ of explicatures and implicatures (cf. Capone, 1997, 2002, 2003, 2008, 2010, 2011a, 2011b). He argues that ‘explicatures’ and ‘intentionality’ are intertwined, and that literal meaning *per se* cannot and should not be the only source of information when it comes to the computation of propositional truth values—a point that I also agree with. He argues that literal meanings need to be enriched (i.e., pragmatically augmented) with pragmatic intrusions if we want to access an honest and comprehensive picture of speakers’ communicative intentions, but he also warns us that this allowance will inevitably make our pragmatic computations non-cancellable whereby allowing pragmatics to ‘overrule’ pragmatics (Fiorin, 2022).

Capone (2019) argues that forms of language can be arranged on a ‘cline’ with ‘forensic’ language use at one end and ‘pidgins’ at the other end. In the former, semantics is the dominant force whereas pragmatics is the dominant force in the latter. Coming from the field of applied linguistics (where quantification, precision, and operational definitions rule), I would argue that the major problem in pragmatics is its tendency towards conceptual rather than operational definitions—at the cost of opacity. Presuppositions, inferences, statements, implicatures, explicatures, entailments, etc. have all been defined conceptually in pragmatics, and have therefore created a lot of confusion and controversy—which would be avoided had they been defined operationally in the first place. I do have operational definitions for these and other pragmatic concepts, but a discussion of them is beyond the scope of the current paper. Another problem with pragmatic views of meaning is that they are all based on Anglo-American linguistic data (i.e., they are Anglo-American-language-specific), and this, too, has created a ‘tunnel-vision’ for people who work in this area. After all, languages are varied, and some are configurational (e.g.,

English), some semi-configurational (e.g., Japanese), and some non-configurational (e.g., Turkish). How can an Anglo-American-language-driven theory account for semi- or non-configurational languages?

The question of ‘what comprises meaning’ gets ever more complicated if we take deconstructionist, anti-essentialist, and sociosemiotic perspectives on the nature of human language into account. A discussion of these topics is beyond the scope of this paper, but the interested reader is invited to see Barthes (1964), Derrida (1981), Eco (1968), Foucault (1970), Landowski (2005), Lotman (1990), Marrone (2021), and Salmani Nodoushan (2021).

5. Discussion

Going back to our analogy of the ‘elephant in a dark room’, it can be argued that all of the scholars who have talked about the nature of ‘meaning’ are right, but none is totally right. Each scholar has thought inside his/her own box and has happened to confirm his/her own biases. By insisting on their own cognitive tunnel visions, they have created a scientific impasse—a deadlock, so to speak—from which they cannot escape, nor are they inclined to do so. Notions that were supposed to be fecund and turn up into a comprehensive, exhaustive, and objective theory of meaning have turned out to be sterile. Nevertheless, I find some merit in the relevance-theoretic perspective on meaning and somehow endorse it, but I still think that that, too, needs to be brushed up through the integration of ‘operational definitions’ of its conceptual claims.

To me, it seems that there is no objective ‘product’ in any language—perhaps with the exception of ‘deontological(ized)’ swears and slurs (I even doubt this since swearing can also be engaged in social functions)—that we can call ‘meaning’. Everything that exists out there is just a ‘process’ of ‘meaning making’, and people bring their own ‘tensions’ (to borrow a term from engineering) to make sense of what they perceive and produce in/through language. This is to divorce the idea that lexemes are ‘containers’ that can contain meaning and to endorse the idea that (a) meaning is ‘poured’ inside lexemes ‘every time’ they are used in language production or comprehension (cf. Mey, 2001), and that (b) ‘tensions’ determine whether the injected meaning will be the same as previous cases or will have to change to fit the use-specific requirements of the speech situation/event.

In Engineering, there is a course called ‘statics’ in which students learn about ‘structural stability’, and later about ‘material strength’. The basic idea is that any material—e.g., a brick in a wall, a tyre on a car, a whole building, etc.—is under pressure or tension from different directions (e.g., x, y, and z axes), but it resists the pressure/tension as long as the ‘resultant force’ is equal to zero. When the resultant force is not equal to zero, the material or structure

experiences what is called 'fatigue' which may result in the collapse of material strength should fatigue persist, and this happens when the material or structure is 'alternatively' loaded with pressure that disrupts the resultant force (e.g., cars pass over a bridge). By the same token, it can be claimed that a lexical item is comprehended to have its previous meaning (i.e., has a 'static' meaning) if no source of fatigue is available to push it out of its comfort zone (i.e., the resultant force is equal to zero), but it assumes a different meaning as soon as some 'factor' or 'thingamabob' disrupts the resultant force.

My idea is that a lexeme is the function of a wide range of factors that contribute to its 'real-time' and 'on-the-spot' interpretation/meaning. To me, it seems that any word is an 'accidental gap'—phoneme cluster allowable by a language 'sound system' such that it does not disrupt the primary function of the human vocal tract (or breathing)—to which some 'sematic content' or 'syntactic relation' has 'arbitrarily' been assigned by the 'collective social intentionality' of language users; the result is a 'teleological' sign capable of retaining its arbitrary meaning/sense as long as the 'resultant force' of all of the factors that impact it is equal to zero. As such, meaning is not static and deontological—although it appears so. A word is not a 'brute' fact, a *la* Anscombe (1958); rather, it is an 'institutional' fact whose truth depends on the existence of 'brute' facts (i.e., its users)—cf. Searle (1995).

Any factor that affects human physiology is doomed to affect language since language is an 'institutional' fact that owes its very existence to the 'brute' fact of human physiology. Needless to say, the human brain—part of human physiology—is a complex electrochemical processing machine that operates on what it demands for its 'metabolic' and 'connectivity' functioning as well as its cognitive, motor, social, and emotional skills. It operates on a given set of factors including glucose, ketone bodies (KBs), potassium, sodium, etc. (Goyal et al., 2018). Anything that affects the human brain, also affects its functions—language and meaning included. When people speak, they encode concepts into thoughts (i.e., subvocalized speech) which they then vocalize as speech. In this process, thoughts are changed into motor orders/directions that set the human vocal tract into motion. The result is a disruption in the air that stands between the speaker's mouth and the hearer's ears (i.e., a set of 'transverse' waves that obey the rules of physics and chemistry). The waves hit the hearer's ear drums, are transmitted to the cochlea through the intervention of the bony ossicles—i.e., the malleus, the incus, and the stapes. The Organ of Corti receives the waves and converts them into electrochemical brain activities which are then processed, decoded and hopefully comprehended by the hearer's brain.

As such, it is not wrong if we claim that language does not exist. The only thing that exists is just a set of waves, some chemicals, some electricity, and a

processing device that gives meaning to all of these. Whatever affects the quality and quantity of any of these factors will also affect the ‘meaning’ that is ‘made’ or ‘produced’ at the end of the line. If the processing device belongs to Humpty Dumpty, ‘glory’ can mean ‘a nice knock-down argument’ conveyed in a scornful tone and accompanied by a contemptuous smile, no matter how ardently Alice objects. On this account, theoreticians of meaning will not see the whole elephant until they wake up from their complacency and confess that it is all about the human ‘brain’. Any foundational ‘theory of meaning’ will inevitably have to be a ‘theory of human brain’—which, of course, is not on a par with ‘binary’ machine computations. The best theory of human brain is perhaps expected to be based on ‘fuzzy’ and/or ‘quantum’ logic. Nevertheless, I do hail Sperber and Wilson (1986, 1995, 2002) for their relevance theory. It still has a long way to go, though.

6. Conclusion

The materials presented hitherto bring us to a general conclusion: meaning is ‘nothing’ but meaning is ‘everything’, and it is not inside what is said; it is what human brain thinks it is. Since human brain can be fooled (e.g., when it goes on cocaine), meaning can change. There is nothing called ‘meaning’, but everything that is called ‘meaning making’.

Going back to the questions I posed in the introduction to this paper, I assume the answers are now self-evident. Does meaning exist at all? I would say no. Is it static or dynamic? I would say meaning is temporarily static as long as the ‘resultant force’ of all of the factors that impact it is equal to zero. Is it *a priori* or *a posteriori*? I would say it is ‘*a posteriori*’ in the sense that the human brain decides—based on its relevance-theoretic operations—which meaning to make. Is meaning a process or a product? I would say it is a process of ‘meaning making’. Is it existent or emergent? I would say it is emergent from context, speaker-hearer relationships, and a multitude of other factors. Is it deontological or teleological? I would say teleological, but sometimes misunderstood as being deontological (as in the case of swearwords and slurs). Can we have an adequate theory of meaning? I would say yes iff it is a theory of human brain and mind. Should such a theory be ‘semantic’, ‘pragmatic’, ‘foundational’, or otherwise? I would say it should be foundational in the sense that it should take human brain and mind into account and see the whole elephant, but not just some part of it. Can ‘symbolic logic’ account for meaning adequately? I would say no, but I reserve the point that ‘adequacy’ is a misleading term. I would rather use the term ‘validity’ to mean that any theory is valid as long as it explains what it claims to explain. All in all, no scientific claim can be exhaustive and comprehensive since we live in a world that itself is relative, but not absolute. Now, the rest for me is silence.

Notes:

1. A monadic or kernel sentence is a simple sentence (one with only one subject and one predicate) with the following features: (1) none of its functions—i.e., subject, verb, object—are repeated; (2) nothing in it is optional; (3) it is only active and positive, but not interrogative, passive, or otherwise; and (4) its internal arguments—if any—are adjectives, nouns, or prepositional locatives. By this token, sentences like 'John is a teacher', 'It was night', 'The lion killed the hyena', and 'Jack is in the park' are kernel, but sentences like 'Is John a teacher?', 'It wasn't night', 'The hyena was killed', and 'Jack and Jill are in the park' are not kernel. Depending on the language at hand, kernel sentences can qualify as zero-place, one-place, two-place, or three-place predicates; the predicator is the core of the kernel sentence (i.e., its 'content' verb, predicate-internal noun, adjective, or prepositional locative—in that order), and the arguments are the other obligatory elements that go around the predicator. The sentence 'It was night', for instance, is a 0-place predicate in that the word 'night' is the predicator—because the verb 'was' is not a content verb, and the subject is not a content word either—i.e., is the pro-subject. 'The lion killed the hyena' is a 2-place predicate in that its content verb 'kill' is the predicator that basically and conceptually-speaking 'has to' require two arguments for its meaning to be complete in reality—i.e., a killer and a killee, or the lion and the hyena—one of which is the external argument (i.e., the subject), and the other is the internal argument (that is the object). As such, this sentence can be written in the form of a 'projection rule' in symbolic logic—i.e., 'kill (lion, hyena)'—which can be read as 'The act of killing is predicated of the lion on the hyena'. The notions of categorization and sub-categorization in grammar also come from these considerations (cf. Yarmohammadi, 2002)—and also Chomsky's conceptions of deep structure in standard theory, extended standard theory, and revised extended standard theory (Chomsky, 1969) as well as his x-bar theory in government and binding (Chomsky, 1981).
2. Likewise, Millianism argues (1) that a proper name has content, and (2) that its content is nothing but the object it stands for (Coates, 2009).

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